

table S1

Table Analyzed	Linneg all repeats				
Two-way ANOVA	Ordinary				
Alpha	0.05				
Source of Variation	% of total variation	P value	P value summary	Significant?	
Interaction	2.866	0.1202	ns	No	
day	4.131	0.0482	*	Yes	
tumour type	12.2	< 0,0001	****	Yes	
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Interaction	82.99	2	41.49	F (2, 122) = 2,156	P = 0,1202
day	19.6	2	59.81	F (2, 122) = 3,108	P = 0,0482
tumour type	353.4	1	353.4	F (1, 122) = 18,36	P < 0,0001
Residual	2348	122	19.25		

Within each column, compare rows (simple effects within columns)												
Number of families	2											
Number of comparisons per family	3											
Alpha	0.05											
Tukey's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff,	95% CI of diff,	Significant?	Summary	Adjusted P Value							
4T1												
D7 vs. D14	0.7838	-2,326 to 3,894	No	ns	0.8215							
D7 vs. D21	-2.35	-5,461 to 0,7599	No	ns	0.1762							
D14 vs. D21	-3.134	-6,139 to -0,1294	Yes	*	0.0388							
4T07												
D7 vs. D14	-2.703	-5,813 to 0,4071	No	ns	0.1021							
D7 vs. D21	-2.561	-6,061 to 0,9394	No	ns	0.1961							
D14 vs. D21	0.1421	-3,449 to 3,734	No	ns	0.9952							
Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff,	SE of diff,	N1	N2	q	DF				
4T1												
D7 vs. D14	4.95	4.17	0.78	131	21	24	0.8456	122				
D7 vs. D21	4.95	7.30	-2.35	131	21	24	2.536	122				
D14 vs. D21	4.17	7.30	-3.13	127	24	24	3.5	122				
4T07												
D7 vs. D14	7.11	9.81	-2.70	131	24	21	2.916	122				
D7 vs. D21	7.11	9.67	-2.56	148	24	14	2.455	122				
D14 vs. D21	9.81	9.67	0.14	151	21	14	0.1328	122				

table S2

Table Analyzed	CAF+ out of linneg all repeats				
Two-way ANOVA	Ordinary				
Alpha	0.05				
Source of Variation	% of total variation	P value	P value summary	Significant?	
Interaction	0.32	0.8064	ns	No	
day	10.02	0.0015	**	Yes	
tumour type	1.45	0.1623	ns	No	
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Interaction	82.83	2	41.41	F (2, 122) = 0.2155	P = 0.8064
day	2636	2	1318	F (2, 122) = 6.858	P = 0.0015
tumour type	379.9	1	379.9	F (1, 122) = 1.977	P = 0.1623
Residual	23445	122	192.2		

Within each column, compare rows (simple effects within columns)												
Number of families	2											
Number of comparisons per family	3											
Alpha	0.05											
Tukey's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff,	95% CI of diff,	Significant?	Summary	Adjusted P Value							
4T1												
D7 vs. D14	7.59	-2,239 to 17,42	No	ns	0.1635							
D7 vs. D21	8.45	-1,383 to 18,27	No	ns	0.1073							
D14 vs. D21	0.86	-8,639 to 10,35	No	ns	0.9751							
4T07												
D7 vs. D14	9.69	-0,1382 to 19,52	No	ns	0.0542							
D7 vs. D21	12.52	1,462 to 23,58	Yes	*	0.0223							
D14 vs. D21	2.83	-8,515 to 14,18	No	ns	0.8245							
Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff,	SE of diff,	N1	N2	q	DF				
4T1												
D7 vs. D14	73.14	65.55	7.59	4.14	21	24	2.591	122				
D7 vs. D21	73.14	64.70	8.45	4.14	21	24	2.883	122				
D14 vs. D21	65.55	64.70	0.86	4.00	24	24	0.3024	122				
4T07												
D7 vs. D14	71.69	62.00	9.69	4.14	24	21	3.308	122				
D7 vs. D21	71.69	59.17	12.52	4.66	24	14	3.799	122				
D14 vs. D21	62.00	59.17	2.83	4.78	21	14	0.8377	122				

table S3

Table Analyzed	CAF+ out of live cells all repeats				
Two-way ANOVA	Ordinary				
Alpha	0.05				
Source of Variation	% of total variation	P value	P value summary	Significant?	
Interaction	2.21	0.2195	ns	No	
day	0.24	0.8467	ns	No	
tumour type	9.14	0.0005	***	Yes	
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Interaction	24.46	2	12.23	F (2, 122) = 1.535	P = 0.2195
day	2.655	2	1.327	F (2, 122) = 0.1667	P = 0.8467
tumour type	10.11	1	10.11	F (1, 122) = 12.69	P = 0.0005
Residual	97.17	122	7.965		

Within each column, compare rows (simple effects within columns)								
Number of families	2							
Number of comparisons per family	3							
Alpha	0.05							
Tukey's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff,	95% CI of diff,	Significant?	Summary	Adjusted P Value			
4T1								
D7 vs. D14	0.94	-1.058 to 2.944	No	ns	0.5046			
D7 vs. D21	-0.37	-2.372 to 1.630	No	ns	0.8989			
D14 vs. D21	-1.31	-3.247 to 0.6188	No	ns	0.244			
4T07								
D7 vs. D14	-0.82	-2.825 to 1.176	No	ns	0.5923			
D7 vs. D21	-0.21	-2.459 to 2.045	No	ns	0.9741			
D14 vs. D21	0.62	-1.693 to 2.928	No	ns	0.8017			
Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff,	SE of diff,	N1	N2	q	DF
4T1								
D7 vs. D14	3.39	2.45	0.94	0.8433	21	24	1.582	122
D7 vs. D21	3.39	3.76	-0.37	0.8433	21	24	0.6221	122
D14 vs. D21	2.45	3.76	-1.31	0.8147	24	24	2.281	122
4T07								
D7 vs. D14	4.67	5.49	-0.82	0.8433	24	21	1.383	122
D7 vs. D21	4.67	4.88	-0.21	0.9491	24	14	0.3086	122
D14 vs. D21	5.49	4.88	0.62	0.9737	21	14	0.8966	122

table S4

Multiple t-tests 4T1 vs 4T07 Lin- out of Live cells								
Day	Discovery?	P value	Mean1 4T1	Mean2 4T07	Difference	SE of difference	t ratio	df
D7		0.039520	4.95	7.11	-2.15	1.01	2.12	43
D14	*	0.000243	4.17	9.81	-5.64	1.41	4.00	43
D21		0.168074	7.30	9.67	-2.36	1.68	1.41	36

Multiple t-tests 4T1 vs 4T07 CAF+ out of Lin- cells								
Day	Discovery?	P value	Mean1 4T1	Mean2 4T07	Difference	SE of difference	t ratio	df
D7		0.761085	73.14	71.69	1.45	4.74	0.31	43
D14		0.273681	65.55	62.00	3.55	3.20	1.11	43
D21		0.268840	64.70	59.17	5.53	4.92	1.12	36

Multiple t-tests 4T1 vs 4T07 CAF+ out of Live cells								
Day	Discovery?	P value	Mean1 4T1	Mean2 4T07	Difference	SE of difference	t ratio	df
D7		0.116181	3.39	4.67	-1.28	0.80	1.60	43
D14	*	0.001006	2.45	5.49	-3.04	0.86	3.53	43
D21		0.266583	3.76	4.88	-1.11	0.99	1.13	36

table S5

Multiple t-tests 4T1 vs 4T07 D7								
CAF marker	Discovery?	P value	Mean1 4T1	Mean2 4T07	Difference	SE of difference	t ratio	df
PDGFRa		0.0363678	48.99	38.28	10.71	4.96	2.16	43
PDGFRb		0.278426	53.38	48.40	4.98	4.54	1.10	43
Podoplanin		0.0041234	55.27	40.49	14.78	4.88	3.03	43
FAP		0.0482698	46.58	51.95	-5.37	2.64	2.03	43
aSMA	*	0.00114589	29.03	19.40	9.63	2.76	3.48	43
CD26		0.0419432	55.93	66.52	-10.58	5.05	2.10	43

Multiple t-tests 4T1 vs 4T07 D14								
CAF marker	Discovery?	P value	Mean1 4T1	Mean2 4T07	Difference	SE of difference	t ratio	df
PDGFRa		0.147984	26.03	19.27	6.76	4.59	1.47	43
PDGFRb		0.0167179	31.32	43.83	-12.51	5.02	2.49	43
Podoplanin		0.0160842	26.11	38.00	-11.89	4.75	2.51	43
FAP		0.0290361	62.45	55.01	7.45	3.30	2.26	43
aSMA	*	0.00013461	9.03	19.92	-10.89	2.60	4.19	43
CD26		0.571223	62.08	64.26	-2.18	3.82	0.57	43

Multiple t-tests 4T1 vs 4T07 D21								
CAF marker	Discovery?	P value	Mean1 4T1	Mean2 4T07	Difference	SE of difference	t ratio	df
PDGFRa	*	0.00138182	18.15	33.19	-15.04	4.34	3.47	36
PDGFRb		0.132781	42.88	32.99	9.89	6.43	1.54	36
Podoplanin		0.0135633	31.49	20.11	11.38	4.38	2.60	36
FAP		0.0904156	61.98	56.44	5.54	3.19	1.74	36
aSMA	*	0.00213947	17.93	7.59	10.34	3.12	3.31	36
CD26	*	8.4759E-06	65.17	47.91	17.26	3.33	5.19	36

4T1

Day 7		① First CAF marker																	
		PDGFRa			PDGFRb			Podoplanin			FAPa			aSMA			CD26		
		Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high
② Subset CAF marker	PDGFRa	100.00	100.00	100.00	50.67	43.01	58.33	65.14	59.10	71.18	38.09	29.13	47.05	49.81	42.43	57.19	45.86	36.29	55.43
	PDGFRb	58.00	50.04	65.96	100.00	100.00	100.00	68.52	61.14	75.90	62.02	57.46	66.57	71.93	64.62	79.24	60.66	53.67	67.65
	Podoplanin	77.70	68.49	86.91	68.42	63.67	73.16	100.00	100.00	100.00	41.52	32.15	50.88	88.92	84.20	93.64	64.04	55.37	72.70
	FAPa	34.55	29.23	39.87	55.69	49.30	62.07	34.26	28.46	40.05	100.00	100.00	100.00	26.32	19.64	32.99	49.32	46.41	52.23
	aSMA	31.62	25.84	37.40	37.84	33.57	42.11	47.37	41.18	53.56	16.07	11.27	20.86	100.00	100.00	100.00	33.11	26.95	39.27
	CD26	52.88	42.70	63.05	62.00	55.79	68.22	63.40	55.97	70.82	59.04	51.98	66.10	60.70	53.69	67.70	100.00	100.00	100.00

Day 14		① First CAF marker																	
		PDGFRa			PDGFRb			Podoplanin			FAPa			aSMA			CD26		
		Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high
② Subset CAF marker	PDGFRa	100.00	100.00	100.00	26.67	19.45	33.89	40.34	33.42	47.26	15.06	10.63	19.50	25.95	20.65	31.24	22.00	14.83	29.18
	PDGFRb	62.74	56.76	68.71	100.00	100.00	100.00	66.43	60.65	72.20	52.21	45.06	59.35	70.22	65.81	74.62	46.62	38.56	54.67
	Podoplanin	84.31	79.56	89.06	55.06	47.71	62.41	100.00	100.00	100.00	27.29	21.02	33.56	88.67	86.59	90.74	43.91	34.39	53.44
	FAPa	46.95	39.76	54.14	67.37	62.77	71.98	43.09	35.59	50.60	100.00	100.00	100.00	31.62	24.98	38.26	49.72	45.16	54.28
	aSMA	27.58	23.21	31.95	29.62	25.50	33.74	46.06	39.87	52.25	10.12	7.19	13.04	100.00	100.00	100.00	19.87	15.27	24.47
	CD26	71.69	66.72	76.65	67.91	63.38	72.44	71.83	66.91	76.76	57.34	54.43	60.25	62.95	58.42	67.49	100.00	100.00	100.00

Day 21		① First CAF marker																	
		PDGFRa			PDGFRb			Podoplanin			FAPa			aSMA			CD26		
		Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high
② Subset CAF marker	PDGFRa	100.00	100.00	100.00	26.74	20.16	33.31	42.85	38.55	47.15	13.88	10.64	17.13	26.07	22.21	29.94	20.66	15.69	25.63
	PDGFRb	56.32	48.39	64.25	100.00	100.00	100.00	66.96	60.11	73.80	47.74	39.82	55.67	71.59	64.28	78.91	46.83	38.40	55.26
	Podoplanin	74.90	65.76	84.03	51.43	42.87	59.99	100.00	100.00	100.00	23.23	17.89	28.58	87.63	84.68	90.58	36.34	29.21	43.47
	FAPa	47.46	41.19	53.73	70.59	65.03	76.14	47.77	39.65	55.89	100.00	100.00	100.00	36.46	29.18	43.74	57.52	54.11	60.92
	aSMA	25.58	19.26	31.90	29.82	22.81	36.84	45.66	40.75	50.58	10.53	6.54	14.52	100.00	100.00	100.00	18.16	13.45	22.87
	CD26	70.56	63.85	77.28	71.27	67.12	75.43	73.88	71.09	76.66	60.35	57.60	63.11	66.14	62.42	69.86	100.00	100.00	100.00

4T07

Day 7		① First CAF marker																	
		PDGFRa			PDGFRb			Podoplanin			FAPa			aSMA			CD26		
		Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high
② Subset CAF marker	PDGFRa	100.00	100.00	100.00	46.06	39.96	52.15	65.84	61.33	70.35	29.68	24.32	35.04	51.11	45.54	56.68	35.77	29.76	41.77
	PDGFRb	60.93	53.01	68.86	100.00	100.00	100.00	73.94	69.47	78.40	57.16	52.16	62.15	80.34	76.63	84.05	54.01	47.07	60.95
	Podoplanin	75.81	65.84	85.79	60.42	55.34	65.51	100.00	100.00	100.00	34.01	29.30	38.71	88.01	83.96	92.06	48.71	41.78	55.65
	FAPa	41.09	36.47	45.72	63.80	58.82	68.78	46.81	40.94	52.68	100.00	100.00	100.00	38.05	31.57	44.54	51.10	48.16	54.05
	aSMA	29.10	23.46	34.75	31.99	27.61	36.38	42.25	37.88	46.62	13.47	10.43	16.51	100.00	100.00	100.00	22.20	18.48	25.93
	CD26	66.62	55.90	77.33	72.07	67.52	76.61	78.21	73.32	83.11	63.88	58.34	69.42	74.91	69.13	80.70	100.00	100.00	100.00

Day 14		① First CAF marker																	
		PDGFRa			PDGFRb			Podoplanin			FAPa			aSMA			CD26		
		Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high
② Subset CAF marker	PDGFRa	100.00	100.00	100.00	35.67	28.90	42.44	58.62	52.58	64.65	19.44	13.47	25.41	50.10	44.13	56.07	23.38	17.04	29.71
	PDGFRb	43.33	36.41	50.25	100.00	100.00	100.00	54.13	47.46	60.79	38.53	31.06	46.00	66.19	61.04	71.34	36.84	28.09	45.58
	Podoplanin	66.72	56.53	76.90	46.78	39.87	53.69	100.00	100.00	100.00	22.76	17.44	28.08	88.07	83.57	92.58	31.27	24.02	38.52
	FAPa	45.55	39.42	51.68	78.53	74.81	82.25	54.76	49.91	59.61	100.00	100.00	100.00	50.95	44.35	57.54	57.50	51.22	63.78
	aSMA	19.89	15.78	24.00	19.99	16.28	23.69	30.66	25.92	35.40	7.11	5.24	8.98	100.00	100.00	100.00	9.73	7.29	12.18
	CD26	62.39	50.86	73.91	71.55	66.32	76.78	73.89	66.94	80.83	55.90	50.75	61.05	66.29	59.84	72.74	100.00	100.00	100.00

Day 21		① First CAF marker																	
		PDGFRa			PDGFRb			Podoplanin			FAPa			aSMA			CD26		
		Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high	Mean	CI95_low	CI95_high
② Subset CAF marker	PDGFRa	100.00	100.00	100.00	34.42	24.70	44.14	59.55	51.54	67.57	20.27	13.43	27.10	47.31	41.62	53.00	25.21	16.60	33.82
	PDGFRb	38.98	25.05	52.91	100.00	100.00	100.00	58.09	47.43	68.74	40.88	30.98	50.77	65.45	52.47	78.43	37.64	26.88	48.40
	Podoplanin	45.10	29.38	60.82	38.22	28.35	48.09	100.00	100.00	100.00	15.72	11.82	19.63	82.57	71.31	93.84	24.73	17.50	31.96
	FAPa	34.45	28.43	40.47	75.58	68.22	82.94	48.50	40.28	56.71	100.00	100.00	100.00	35.98	27.41	44.55	56.77	50.52	63.02
	aSMA	14.22	7.99	20.45	15.49	10.16	20.82	29.70	21.98	37.42	4.16	2.67	5.65	100.00	100.00	100.00	6.84	4.53	9.15
	CD26	42.43	29.01	55.85	56.74	49.29	64.18	59.70	51.50	67.90	47.12	43.03	51.21	46.53	37.30	55.76	100.00	100.00	100.00

table S8

Top	4T1 D7				4T1 D14				4T1 D21			
	CAF subset	Mean %	SEM	n	CAF subset	Mean %	SEM	n	CAF subset	Mean %	SEM	n
1	S56	8.07	1.17	21	S32	16.45	3.13	24	S32	15.09	1.96	24
2	S63	7.07	2.14	21	S56	13.98	1.34	24	S56	14.55	0.76	24
3	S22	6.87	0.85	21	S22	10.38	1.31	24	S22	13.21	2.03	24
4	S32	5.84	1.33	21	S24	8.11	0.96	24	S24	11.35	1.23	24
5	S17	5.82	0.88	21	S54	6.41	0.95	24	S54	6.19	1.25	24
6	S27	4.83	1.20	21	S10	3.84	0.60	24	S10	2.97	0.52	24
7	S54	4.45	0.48	21	S27	3.78	1.06	24	S17	2.72	0.32	24
8	S9	4.20	0.63	21	S17	3.39	0.51	24	S18	2.09	0.28	24
9	S10	3.78	0.59	21	S42	2.72	0.57	24	S25	2.02	0.38	24
10	S41	3.56	0.71	21	S18	2.49	0.18	24	S2	1.97	0.21	24
11	S1	3.55	0.75	21	S12	2.07	0.32	24	S27	1.92	0.43	24
12	S24	3.24	0.61	21	S2	1.94	0.24	24	S42	1.79	0.33	24
13	S57	3.23	0.44	21	S25	1.92	0.34	24	S1	1.66	0.35	24
14	S25	2.59	0.31	21	S1	1.66	0.29	24	S9	1.50	0.24	24
15	S42	2.44	0.44	21	S62	1.66	0.25	24	S62	1.47	0.14	24
16	S59	2.15	0.31	21	S44	1.47	0.36	24	S63	1.45	0.34	24
17	S62	2.06	0.30	21	S28	1.46	0.31	24	S12	1.35	0.23	24
18	S19	2.02	0.53	21	S63	1.40	0.65	24	S20	1.17	0.17	24
19	S12	1.95	0.37	21	S9	1.36	0.17	24	S44	1.13	0.25	24
20	S11	1.92	0.45	21	S19	1.14	0.28	24	S19	1.10	0.21	24
21	S18	1.74	0.17	21	S20	1.05	0.17	24	S48	1.06	0.27	24
22	S2	1.40	0.18	21	S48	0.90	0.14	24	S55	0.82	0.23	24
23	S49	1.28	0.12	21	S26	0.85	0.12	24	S60	0.69	0.10	24
24	S55	1.27	0.44	21	S41	0.74	0.15	24	S28	0.64	0.08	24
25	S48	1.16	0.22	21	S50	0.70	0.06	24	S26	0.64	0.11	24
26	S21	1.04	0.18	21	S58	0.67	0.11	24	S11	0.59	0.12	24
27	S28	1.00	0.21	21	S57	0.65	0.11	24	S23	0.57	0.08	24
28	S58	0.95	0.17	21	S60	0.62	0.05	24	S52	0.55	0.08	24
29	S44	0.81	0.09	21	S11	0.58	0.16	24	S41	0.53	0.08	24
30	S26	0.71	0.09	21	S52	0.53	0.08	24	S50	0.53	0.05	24
31	S20	0.70	0.12	21	S34	0.48	0.05	24	S57	0.52	0.08	24
32	S43	0.67	0.08	21	S46	0.45	0.07	24	S58	0.50	0.09	24
33	S50	0.61	0.09	21	S59	0.44	0.07	24	S4	0.46	0.14	24
34	S3	0.59	0.20	21	S55	0.44	0.12	24	S59	0.46	0.10	24
35	S60	0.58	0.06	21	S30	0.38	0.05	24	S34	0.45	0.06	24
36	S53	0.57	0.10	21	S4	0.32	0.08	24	S30	0.43	0.04	24
37	S33	0.51	0.06	21	S49	0.31	0.03	24	S21	0.38	0.06	24
38	S46	0.51	0.09	21	S21	0.26	0.03	24	S31	0.37	0.18	24
39	S31	0.50	0.14	21	S40	0.23	0.05	24	S40	0.31	0.09	24
40	S23	0.44	0.08	21	S36	0.19	0.05	24	S49	0.31	0.03	24
41	S4	0.40	0.13	21	S43	0.18	0.04	24	S3	0.29	0.09	24
42	S51	0.39	0.05	21	S23	0.17	0.03	24	S36	0.28	0.09	24
43	S52	0.37	0.09	21	S3	0.16	0.05	24	S43	0.25	0.07	24
44	S34	0.35	0.05	21	S31	0.16	0.06	24	S46	0.24	0.03	24
45	S61	0.34	0.07	21	S33	0.16	0.03	24	S33	0.22	0.06	24
46	S30	0.19	0.03	21	S51	0.10	0.02	24	S16	0.21	0.06	24
47	S6	0.18	0.04	21	S8	0.09	0.03	24	S8	0.21	0.05	24
48	S38	0.16	0.04	21	S53	0.09	0.01	24	S6	0.15	0.02	24
49	S40	0.16	0.04	21	S16	0.09	0.02	24	S51	0.13	0.03	24
50	S36	0.11	0.02	21	S38	0.08	0.01	24	S38	0.11	0.02	24
51	S35	0.10	0.02	21	S6	0.08	0.01	24	S53	0.10	0.02	24
52	S8	0.10	0.03	21	S61	0.08	0.03	24	S61	0.07	0.02	24
53	S29	0.08	0.02	21	S14	0.05	0.01	24	S35	0.05	0.02	24
54	S14	0.08	0.02	21	S35	0.03	0.01	24	S29	0.04	0.01	24
55	S16	0.07	0.01	21	S29	0.02	0.00	24	S14	0.03	0.01	24
56	S45	0.07	0.02	21	S45	0.01	0.00	24	S47	0.03	0.01	24
57	S5	0.07	0.02	21	S5	0.01	0.00	24	S5	0.02	0.01	24
58	S47	0.06	0.01	21	S47	0.01	0.00	24	S37	0.01	0.00	24
59	S7	0.03	0.01	21	S37	0.00	0.00	24	S39	0.01	0.00	24
60	S15	0.03	0.01	21	S39	0.00	0.00	24	S7	0.01	0.00	24
61	S37	0.02	0.01	21	S7	0.00	0.00	24	S45	0.01	0.00	24
62	S39	0.02	0.01	21	S15	0.00	0.00	24	S15	0.01	0.00	24
63	S13	0.01	0.00	21	S13	0.00	0.00	24	S13	0.00	0.00	24

table S9

Top	4T07 D7				4T07 D14				4T07 D21			
	CAF subset	Mean %	SEM	n	CAF subset	Mean %	SEM	n	CAF subset	Mean %	SEM	n
1	S32	14.44	1.94	24	S56	17.73	1.08	21	S56	16.88	1.21	14
2	S56	9.48	0.82	24	S32	17.32	2.50	21	S32	13.72	2.49	14
3	S22	9.39	1.05	24	S24	12.32	1.61	21	S63	13.69	4.41	14
4	S24	7.23	0.94	24	S22	9.88	1.43	21	S24	8.95	1.49	14
5	S63	6.49	2.62	24	S63	6.03	3.02	21	S22	8.91	1.89	14
6	S17	5.33	0.48	24	S54	4.70	1.02	21	S54	7.66	1.82	14
7	S54	4.52	0.52	24	S27	3.56	0.84	21	S27	2.45	0.72	14
8	S9	4.48	0.60	24	S17	3.29	0.56	21	S55	2.31	0.70	14
9	S25	3.55	0.52	24	S19	1.94	0.42	21	S17	2.10	0.42	14
10	S1	3.15	0.59	24	S18	1.88	0.24	21	S62	1.72	0.40	14
11	S10	2.97	0.57	24	S1	1.59	0.30	21	S21	1.17	0.24	14
12	S27	2.96	0.52	24	S55	1.52	0.48	21	S25	1.13	0.34	14
13	S18	2.07	0.21	24	S20	1.33	0.19	21	S19	1.12	0.29	14
14	S2	1.78	0.16	24	S25	1.16	0.18	21	S31	1.06	0.41	14
15	S57	1.70	0.31	24	S2	1.09	0.15	21	S23	1.02	0.20	14
16	S19	1.52	0.22	24	S28	0.97	0.22	21	S42	0.99	0.37	14
17	S62	1.36	0.12	24	S62	0.89	0.16	21	S18	0.91	0.11	14
18	S55	1.18	0.46	24	S9	0.88	0.17	21	S41	0.84	0.20	14
19	S41	1.04	0.20	24	S52	0.71	0.10	21	S61	0.80	0.18	14
20	S59	1.02	0.17	24	S21	0.69	0.19	21	S1	0.76	0.17	14
21	S11	0.94	0.19	24	S11	0.61	0.14	21	S59	0.71	0.17	14
22	S28	0.88	0.13	24	S60	0.57	0.10	21	S9	0.71	0.24	14
23	S26	0.87	0.19	24	S10	0.56	0.13	21	S50	0.68	0.13	14
24	S49	0.77	0.09	24	S41	0.55	0.11	21	S20	0.66	0.10	14
25	S21	0.76	0.09	24	S42	0.55	0.16	21	S57	0.63	0.12	14
26	S42	0.74	0.12	24	S50	0.54	0.12	21	S44	0.62	0.20	14
27	S20	0.72	0.09	24	S23	0.53	0.08	21	S60	0.62	0.14	14
28	S12	0.69	0.11	24	S31	0.48	0.14	21	S48	0.59	0.27	14
29	S48	0.66	0.12	24	S3	0.45	0.12	21	S49	0.58	0.10	14
30	S23	0.62	0.08	24	S57	0.44	0.08	21	S58	0.58	0.20	14
31	S53	0.52	0.17	24	S59	0.43	0.07	21	S28	0.57	0.17	14
32	S61	0.51	0.11	24	S12	0.36	0.06	21	S53	0.56	0.11	14
33	S58	0.44	0.10	24	S61	0.36	0.09	21	S10	0.53	0.21	14
34	S30	0.43	0.07	24	S44	0.35	0.05	21	S2	0.39	0.08	14
35	S31	0.43	0.09	24	S49	0.35	0.06	21	S11	0.33	0.10	14
36	S50	0.41	0.06	24	S34	0.31	0.05	21	S52	0.32	0.06	14
37	S6	0.40	0.15	24	S48	0.29	0.07	21	S51	0.31	0.11	14
38	S60	0.35	0.07	24	S51	0.28	0.08	21	S26	0.29	0.10	14
39	S51	0.31	0.07	24	S30	0.27	0.06	21	S12	0.25	0.07	14
40	S3	0.27	0.06	24	S26	0.26	0.05	21	S34	0.24	0.06	14
41	S46	0.27	0.03	24	S4	0.25	0.07	21	S30	0.23	0.06	14
42	S44	0.26	0.05	24	S53	0.24	0.04	21	S33	0.21	0.05	14
43	S33	0.25	0.03	24	S58	0.23	0.05	21	S43	0.20	0.06	14
44	S34	0.24	0.03	24	S33	0.23	0.04	21	S3	0.19	0.10	14
45	S4	0.22	0.05	24	S43	0.20	0.04	21	S29	0.09	0.05	14
46	S52	0.22	0.03	24	S6	0.16	0.07	21	S46	0.09	0.02	14
47	S43	0.22	0.04	24	S36	0.12	0.02	21	S4	0.09	0.03	14
48	S38	0.18	0.08	24	S40	0.08	0.01	21	S36	0.08	0.03	14
49	S40	0.17	0.04	24	S8	0.08	0.02	21	S6	0.07	0.02	14
50	S29	0.14	0.03	24	S29	0.07	0.02	21	S7	0.06	0.06	14
51	S8	0.09	0.02	24	S38	0.07	0.02	21	S38	0.05	0.02	14
52	S16	0.08	0.01	24	S35	0.06	0.02	21	S40	0.05	0.02	14
53	S36	0.08	0.01	24	S46	0.06	0.02	21	S47	0.05	0.03	14
54	S14	0.06	0.01	24	S16	0.05	0.02	21	S5	0.05	0.03	14
55	S35	0.04	0.01	24	S47	0.02	0.01	21	S16	0.04	0.02	14
56	S45	0.03	0.01	24	S39	0.01	0.01	21	S8	0.04	0.01	14
57	S47	0.02	0.00	24	S14	0.01	0.00	21	S35	0.02	0.01	14
58	S5	0.02	0.00	24	S7	0.01	0.00	21	S14	0.02	0.01	14
59	S15	0.01	0.00	24	S5	0.01	0.00	21	S45	0.02	0.00	14
60	S13	0.01	0.00	24	S15	0.01	0.00	21	S15	0.01	0.01	14
61	S37	0.01	0.00	24	S45	0.01	0.00	21	S39	0.01	0.00	14
62	S7	0.01	0.00	24	S13	0.00	0.00	21	S37	0.01	0.00	14
63	S39	0.00	0.00	24	S37	0.00	0.00	21	S13	0.00	0.00	14

table S10

Multiple t-tests 4T1 vs 4T07 D7								Multiple t-tests 4T1 vs 4T07 D14								Multiple t-tests 4T1 vs 4T07 D21										
CAF subset	Discovery?	P value	Mean1 4T1	Mean2 4T07	Difference	SE of difference	t ratio	df	CAF subset	Discovery?	P value	Mean1 4T1	Mean2 4T07	Difference	SE of difference	t ratio	df	CAF subset	Discovery?	P value	Mean1 4T1	Mean2 4T07	Difference	SE of difference	t ratio	df
S1		0.67028	3.55	3.15	0.41	0.94	0.429	43	S1		0.86289	1.66	1.59	0.07	0.42	0.175	43	S1		0.066789	1.66	0.76	0.90	0.47	1.890	36
S2		0.115340	1.40	1.78	-0.38	0.24	1.607	43	S2		0.005825	1.94	1.09	0.85	0.29	2.902	43	S2	*	0.000003	1.97	0.39	1.58	0.29	5.503	36
S3		0.13867	0.59	0.27	0.31	0.19	1.614	43	S3		0.018291	0.16	0.45	-0.29	0.12	2.453	43	S3		0.506516	0.29	0.19	0.09	0.14	0.671	36
S4		0.97771	0.40	0.22	0.17	0.13	1.308	43	S4		0.521111	0.32	0.25	0.07	0.11	0.647	43	S4		0.045289	0.46	0.09	0.38	0.18	2.074	36
S5		0.00619	0.07	0.02	0.05	0.02	2.884	43	S5		0.641022	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.470	43	S5		0.223138	0.02	0.05	-0.03	0.02	1.240	36
S6		0.94937	0.18	0.40	-0.22	0.17	1.317	43	S6		0.225444	0.08	0.16	-0.08	0.07	1.231	43	S6		0.019330	0.15	0.07	0.09	0.03	2.648	36
S7		0.018639	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.01	2.445	43	S7		0.066966	0.00	0.01	-0.01	0.00	1.879	43	S7		0.211691	0.01	0.06	-0.05	0.04	1.272	36
S8		0.775064	0.10	0.09	0.01	0.03	0.288	43	S8		0.672961	0.09	0.08	0.02	0.04	0.425	43	S8		0.079864	0.21	0.04	0.17	0.07	2.482	36
S9		0.750949	4.20	4.48	-0.28	0.87	0.319	43	S9		0.053233	1.36	0.88	0.48	0.24	1.988	43	S9		0.038304	1.50	0.71	0.79	0.37	2.51	36
S10		0.332852	3.78	2.97	0.80	0.82	0.979	43	S10	*	0.000009	3.84	0.56	3.28	0.65	5.047	43	S10		0.001291	2.97	0.53	2.44	0.70	3.491	36
S11		0.041256	1.92	0.94	0.98	0.47	2.104	43	S11		0.899971	0.58	0.61	-0.03	0.22	0.126	43	S11		0.568885	0.59	0.33	0.26	0.18	1.446	36
S12	*	0.001220	1.95	0.69	1.26	0.36	3.463	43	S12	*	0.000014	2.07	0.36	1.70	0.35	4.905	43	S12	*	0.000094	1.35	0.25	1.10	0.31	3.614	36
S13		0.708238	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.377	43	S13		0.439272	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.781	43	S13		0.839347	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.204	36
S14		0.384671	0.08	0.06	0.02	0.02	0.878	43	S14	*	0.000169	0.05	0.01	0.04	0.01	4.140	43	S14		0.209145	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.01	1.279	36
S15		0.149474	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	1.468	43	S15		0.216424	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	1.255	43	S15		0.203697	0.01	0.01	-0.01	0.01	1.295	36
S16		0.574243	0.07	0.08	-0.01	0.02	0.566	43	S16		0.192132	0.09	0.05	0.04	0.03	1.325	43	S16		0.038017	0.21	0.04	0.17	0.08	2.54	36
S17		0.620748	5.82	5.33	0.48	0.97	0.498	43	S17		0.894037	3.39	3.29	0.10	0.76	0.134	43	S17		0.243631	2.72	2.10	0.62	0.52	1.85	36
S18		0.237856	1.74	2.07	-0.33	0.28	1.197	43	S18		0.042731	2.49	1.88	0.62	0.30	2.088	43	S18		0.003042	2.09	0.91	1.18	0.37	3.78	36
S19		0.369887	2.02	1.52	0.50	0.55	0.906	43	S19		0.108571	1.14	1.94	-0.80	0.49	1.639	43	S19		0.955422	1.10	1.12	-0.02	0.35	0.056	36
S20		0.871153	0.70	0.72	-0.02	0.15	0.83	43	S20		0.285773	1.05	1.33	-0.28	0.26	1.081	43	S20		0.034774	1.17	0.66	0.51	0.23	2.14	36
S21		0.159622	1.04	0.76	0.28	0.20	1.431	43	S21		0.022461	0.26	0.69	-0.43	0.18	2.368	43	S21	*	0.000303	0.38	1.17	-0.79	0.20	3.988	36
S22		0.072977	6.87	9.39	-2.53	1.37	1.838	43	S22		0.798111	10.28	9.88	0.50	1.94	0.257	43	S22		0.164183	13.21	8.91	4.29	3.02	1.420	36
S23		0.123318	0.44	0.62	-0.17	0.11	1.572	43	S23	*	0.000080	0.17	0.53	-0.36	0.08	4.359	43	S23		0.020824	0.57	1.02	-0.45	0.19	2.417	36
S24	*	0.001268	3.24	7.23	-3.99	1.16	3.450	43	S24		0.025527	8.11	12.32	-4.21	1.82	2.314	43	S24		0.230951	11.35	8.95	2.40	1.97	1.219	36
S25		0.14095	2.59	3.55	-0.96	0.63	1.527	43	S25		0.069355	1.92	1.16	0.76	0.41	1.863	43	S25		0.124650	2.02	1.13	0.89	0.56	1.572	36
S26		0.463034	0.71	0.87	-0.16	0.22	0.740	43	S26	*	0.000081	0.85	0.26	0.59	0.13	4.356	43	S26		0.039129	0.64	0.29	0.35	0.16	2.141	36
S27		0.142809	4.83	2.96	1.87	1.25	1.494	43	S27		0.870810	3.78	3.56	0.23	1.38	0.164	43	S27		0.502708	1.92	2.45	-0.53	0.78	0.677	36
S28		0.631965	1.00	0.88	0.12	0.24	0.482	43	S28		0.218536	1.46	0.97	0.49	0.39	1.249	43	S28		0.688840	0.64	0.57	0.07	0.17	0.406	36
S29		0.089995	0.08	0.14	-0.06	0.03	1.757	43	S29		0.002540	0.02	0.07	-0.05	0.02	3.206	43	S29		0.167042	0.04	0.09	-0.06	0.04	1.410	36
S30		0.006813	0.19	0.43	-0.23	0.08	2.843	43	S30		0.148259	0.38	0.27	0.11	0.07	1.472	43	S30		0.004817	0.43	0.23	0.21	0.07	3.005	36
S31		0.665055	0.50	0.43	0.07	0.16	0.436	43	S31		0.030607	0.16	0.48	-0.32	0.14	2.236	43	S31		0.088126	0.37	1.06	-0.68	0.39	1.753	36
S32	*	0.000918	5.84	14.44	-8.60	2.41	3.561	43	S32		0.832101	16.45	17.32	-0.87	4.08	0.213	43	S32		0.669595	15.09	13.72	1.38	3.20	0.430	36
S33	*	0.000139	0.51	0.25	0.26	0.06	4.183	43	S33		0.119713	0.16	0.23	-0.08	0.05	1.588	43	S33		0.853266	0.22	0.21	0.02	0.08	0.186	36
S34		0.082846	0.35	0.24	0.10	0.06	1.776	43	S34		0.018420	0.48	0.31	0.17	0.07	2.450	43	S34		0.028409	0.45	0.24	0.21	0.09	2.283	36
S35		0.015673	0.10	0.04	0.06	0.02	2.516	43	S35		0.144486	0.03	0.06	-0.03	0.02	1.318	43	S35		0.214440	0.05	0.02	0.03	0.02	1.264	36
S36		0.203425	0.11	0.08	0.03	0.02	1.221	43	S36		0.235245	0.19	0.12	0.07	0.06	1.204	43	S36		0.095830	0.28	0.08	0.20	0.12	1.710	36
S37		0.032380	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	2.112	43	S37		0.202029	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.296	43	S37		0.375778	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.897	36
S38		0.782050	0.16	0.18	-0.03	0.10	0.278	43	S38		0.477959	0.08	0.07	0.01	0.02	0.716	43	S38		0.053825	0.11	0.05	0.06	0.03	1.994	36
S39		0.039842	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.01	2.120	43	S39		0.195444	0.00	0.01	-0.01	0.01	1.315	43	S39		0.531654	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.632	36
S40		0.788940	0.16	0.17	-0.02	0.06	0.269	43	S40		0.018852	0.23	0.08	0.15	0.06	2.566	43	S40		0.028662	0.31	0.05	0.26	0.11	2.311	36
S41	*	0.000789	3.56	1.04	2.52	0.70	3.612	43	S41		0.321236	0.74	0.55	0.19	0.19	1.003	43	S41		0.104877	0.53	0.84	-0.31	0.19	1.664	36
S42	*	0.000322	2.44	0.74	1.69	0.43	3.911	43	S42	*	0.001271	2.72	0.55	2.18	0.63	3.449	43	S42		0.126384	1.79	0.99	0.81	0.52	1.565	36
S43	*	0.000008	0.67	0.22	0.45	0.09	5.074	43	S43		0.743423	0.18	0.20	-0.02	0.05	0.329	43	S43		0.688055	0.25	0.20	0.04	0.10	0.407	36
S44	*	0.000001	0.81	0.26	0.55	0.10	5.590	43	S44		0.006553	1.47	0.35	1.12	0.39	2.858	43	S44		0.162772	1.13	0.62	0.51	0.36	1.425	36
S45		0.044907	0.07	0.03	0.04	0.02	2.066	43	S45		0.225895	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	1.229	43	S45		0.060755	0.01	0.02	-0.01	0.00	1.936	36
S46		0.010461	0.51	0.27	0.24	0.09	2.677	43	S46	*	0.000007	0.45	0.06	0.39	0.08	5.109	43	S46		0.001589	0.24	0.09	0.15	0.05	3.416	36
S47		0.002508	0.06	0.02	0.03	0.01	3.211	43	S47		0.046365	0.01	0.02	-0.02	0.01	2.051	43	S47		0.500512	0.03	0.05	-0.02	0.02	0.681	36
S48		0.043457	1.16	0.66	0.51	0.24	2.081	43	S48	*	0.000469	0.90	0.29	0.61	0.16	3.787	43	S48		0.252844	1.06	0.59	0.48	0.41	1.162	36
S49	*	0.001231	1.28	0.77	0.51	0.15	3.460	43	S49		0.618470	0.31	0.35	-0.03	0.06	0.502	43	S49		0.004597	0.31	0.58	-0.27	0.09	3.023	36
S50		0.050778	0.61	0.41	0.20	0.10	2.010	43	S50		0.229197	0.70	0.54	0.16	0.13	1.220	43	S50		0.227580	0.53	0.68	-0.15	0.12	1.228	36
S51		0.388689	0.39	0.31	0.08	0.09	0.871	43	S51		0.027193	0.10	0.28	-0.18	0.08	2.287	43	S51		0.066808	0.13	0.31	-0.17	0.09	1.8	